

Competency Questions for the Open Energy Knowledge Graph

Table 1. List of Competency Questions in natural language that request the OEKG to provide all entities of a certain type (bundle, scenario, data set, DOI) that fulfill certain specifications: “Give me all [entities of type] with [specification].”

“Give me all [entities of type] with [specification].”		
No.	type	specification
CQ1	... bundles	in which <i>institution A</i> was involved.
CQ2	... bundles	that cover, among others, the <i>energy transformation sector</i> and the <i>industry sector</i> .
CQ3	... bundles	that cover only the <i>energy transformation sector</i> .
CQ4	... bundles	that have the <i>sufficiency</i> descriptor tag and have a scenario for the year <i>2040</i> .
CQ5	... bundles	to which <i>person P</i> contributed as author to a publication.
CQ6	... scenarios	that have <i>data set B</i> as input data.
CQ7	... scenarios	that have <i>data set B</i> as output data.
CQ8	... scenarios	that belong to <i>bundle C</i> or <i>bundle D</i> .
CQ9	... scenarios	of type target driven scenarios that are for <i>Germany</i> and project the year <i>2050 or later</i> .
CQ10	... scenarios	about <i>Germany</i> , either as <i>study region</i> or <i>interacting region</i> , and project the year <i>2030</i> .
CQ11	... scenarios	that are for <i>Germany</i> and project the year <i>2030</i> , where the respective bundle covers the <i>energy transformation sector</i> .
CQ12	... data sets	that are part of <i>scenario E</i> .
CQ13	... data sets	that are part of <i>bundle C</i> .
CQ14	... scenarios	that belong to a bundle that is modeled within the <i>framework F</i> .
CQ15	... bundles	that are modeled within the <i>framework F</i> .
CQ16	... scenarios	that belong to a bundle that is modeled with the <i>model M</i> .
CQ17	... bundles	that are modeled with the <i>model M</i> .
CQ18	... scenarios	that belong to a bundle modeled with the <i>model M</i> and that project the years <i>2030</i> and <i>2040</i> .
CQ19	... DOIs	of publications that are about a bundle that contain a scenario for the year <i>2050</i> .
CQ20	... data sets	of <i>scenario E</i> that contain data for the year <i>2030</i> .

Translation of Competency Questions from natural language into SPARQL

CQ1. Give me all bundles in which the institution 'Fraunhofer ISI' was involved.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?label WHERE{
?s ?p ?o.
?p rdfs:label "has organisation"^^XSD:string.
?o rdfs:label "Fraunhofer ISI"^^XSD:string.
?s rdfs:label ?label.}
```

CQ2. Give me all bundles that cover, amongst others, the energy transformation sector and industry sector.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?label WHERE{
?covers_sector rdfs:label "covers sector (shortcut)".
?s ?covers_sector ?o.
?o a*/rdfs:subClassOf* ?sec.
?s rdfs:label ?label.
?energy_transformation_sector rdfs:label "energy transformation sector".
?industry_sector rdfs:label "industry sector".
FILTER(?sec = ?energy_transformation_sector || ?sec = ?industry_sector).
}
```

CQ3. Give me all bundles that cover only the energy transformation sector.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name WHERE{
{
?s oeo:OE0_00020439 ?o.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?o a*/rdfs:subClassOf* oeo:OE0_00000158.
}
MINUS
{
?s oeo:OE0_00020439 ?o.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?s oeo:OE0_00020439 ?o2.
?o a*/rdfs:subClassOf* oeo:OE0_00000158.
?o2 a*/rdfs:subClassOf* ?sec2.
FILTER(?sec2 != oeo:OE0_00000158 && ?o != ?o2)
}
}
```

CQ4. Give me all bundles that have the sufficiency descriptor tag and have a scenario for the year 2040.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name WHERE{
?s oeo:OEO_00390071 ?o.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?o rdfs:label "sufficiency"^^XSD:string.
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?scenario.
?scenario a oeo:OEO_00000365.
?scenario oeo:OEO_00020440 ?year.
FILTER CONTAINS(str(?year), "2040")
}
```

CQ5. Give me all bundles to which Jane Smith contributed as author to a publication.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name ?pub ?publabel WHERE{
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?pub.
?pub a oeo:OEO_00020012.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?pub oeo:OEO_00000506 ?author.
?pub rdfs:label ?publabel.
?author rdfs:label "Jane Smith"^^XSD:string.
}
```

CQ6. Give me all scenarios that have dataset "abb_simulation_parameter" as input data.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name WHERE{
?s oeo:OEO_00020437 ?input.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?input rdfs:label "abb_simulation_parameter"^^XSD:string.
}
```

CQ7. Give me all scenario that have dataset "Primary and final energy consumption of scenario KS95" as output data.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name WHERE{
?s a oeo:OEO_00000365.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?s oeo:OEO_00020436 ?output.
?output rdfs:label "Primary and final energy consumption of scenario KS95"^^XSD:string.
}
```

CQ8. Give me all scenarios that belong to bundle C or bundle D.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oekg: <http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oekg/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name ?scenario ?scenlabel WHERE{
  ?s obo:BF0_0000051 ?scenario.
  ?s rdfs:label ?name.
  ?scenario a oeo:OEO_00000365.
  ?scenario rdfs:label ?scenlabel.
  FILTER(?s = oekg:59cf408f-8ab1-7fe1-0175-e3e50e15eeaa ||
  ?s = oekg:8a59cb1b-ea99-0594-a5ef-7d59f1b7fab3).
}
```

CQ9. Give me all scenarios of type target driven scenarios that are for Germany and project the year 2050 or later.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name ?year WHERE{
  ?s oeo:OEO_00390073 oeo:OEO_00020247.
  ?s rdfs:label ?name.
  ?s oeo:OEO_00020220 ?land.
  ?land rdfs:label "Germany"^^XSD:string.
  ?s oeo:OEO_00020440 ?year.
  FILTER (?year >= "2050-01-01"^^XSD:dateTime).
}
```

CQ10. Give me all scenarios about Germany, either as study region or interacting region, and project the year 2030.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name WHERE{
  {?s oeo:OEO_00020220 ?land.
  ?s rdfs:label ?name.
  ?land rdfs:label "Germany"^^XSD:string.
  ?s oeo:OEO_00020440 ?year.}
  UNION
  {?s oeo:OEO_00020222 ?land.
  ?s rdfs:label ?name.
  ?land rdfs:label "Germany"^^XSD:string.
  ?s oeo:OEO_00020440 ?year.}
  FILTER CONTAINS(str(?year),"2030")
}
```

CQ11. Give me all scenarios that are for Germany and project the year 2030, where the respective bundle covers the energy transformation sector.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?scenario ?scenename ?s ?name WHERE{
?s oeo:OE0_00020439 ?o.
?o a*/rdfs:subClassOf* oeo:OE0_00000158.
?s obo:BF0_0000051 ?scenario.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?scenario a oeo:OE0_00000365.
?scenario rdfs:label ?scenename.
?scenario oeo:OE0_00020220 ?land.
?land rdfs:label "Germany"^^XSD:string.
?scenario oeo:OE0_00020440 ?year.
FILTER CONTAINS(str(?year),"2030")
}
```

CQ12. Give me all datasets that are part of scenario E.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX oekgsc: <http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oekg/scenario/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?dataset ?label WHERE{
oekgsc:444fca1a-8e8f-1e56-9773-6852691621b0 ?p ?dataset.
?dataset rdfs:label ?label.
FILTER(?p = oeo:OE0_00020436 || ?p = oeo:OE0_00020437).
}
```

CQ13. Give me all datasets that are part of bundle C.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX oekg: <http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oekg/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?dataset ?name WHERE{
oekg:6ddf7ede-c3a5-93c8-4385-b975c628d610 obo:BF0_0000051 ?scenario.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?scenario a oeo:OE0_00000365.
?scenario ?p ?dataset.
?dataset rdfs:label ?name.
FILTER(?p = oeo:OE0_00020436 || ?p = oeo:OE0_00020437).
}
```

CQ14. Give me all scenarios that belong to a bundle that is modelled within the MES-SAGEix framework.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?scen ?name WHERE{
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?f.
?f a oeo:OEO_00000172.
?f rdfs:label "MESSAGEix"^^XSD:string.
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?scen.
?scenario a oeo:OEO_00000365.
?scen rdfs:label ?name.
}
```

CQ15. Give me all bundles that are modelled within the MESSAGEix framework.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name WHERE{
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?f.
?f a oeo:OEO_00000172.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?f rdfs:label "MESSAGEix"^^XSD:string.
}
```

CQ16. Give me all scenarios that belong to a bundle that is modelled with the oemof abbb model.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?scen ?name WHERE{
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?m.
?m a oeo:OEO_00000277.
?m rdfs:label "oemof_abbb"^^XSD:string.
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?scen.
?scen a oeo:OEO_00000365.
?scen rdfs:label ?name.
}
```

CQ17. Give me all bundles that are modelled with the oemof abbb model.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?s ?name WHERE{
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?m.
?m a oeo:OEO_00000277.
?s rdfs:label ?name.
?m rdfs:label "oemof_abbb"^^XSD:string.
}
```

CQ18. Give me all scenarios that belong to a bundle modelled with the oemof abbb model and that project the years 2030 and 2040.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
PREFIX XSD: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?scen ?name WHERE{
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?m. #has part
?m a oeo:OEO_00000277. #model factsheet
?m rdfs:label "oemof_abbb"^^XSD:string.
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?scen. #has part
?scen a oeo:OEO_00000365. #scenario factsheet
?scen rdfs:label ?name.
?scen oeo:OEO_00020440 ?year. #has scenario year value
FILTER (CONTAINS(str(?year), "2030")||CONTAINS(str(?year), "2040")).
}
```

C19. Give me all DOIs of publications that are about a bundle that contain a scenario for the year 2050.

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX oeo: <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?d ?p ?name WHERE{
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?p.
?p rdfs:label ?name.
?p a oeo:OEO_00020012.
?p oeo:OEO_00390098 ?d.
?s obo:BFO_0000051 ?scen.
?scen a oeo:OEO_00000365.
?scen oeo:OEO_00020440 ?year.
FILTER CONTAINS(str(?year), "2050").
}
```